

Realizing Intent-driven Network Management with TM Forum Standards

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Abstract—This paper details the realization of Intent-driven Management with TM Forum standards. As networks become more autonomous, a key challenge is balancing customer needs with network and resource operations. Intent-based networking (IBN) offers a solution by abstracting service expectations and implementation complexities. We propose an architecture for IBN that follows the TM Forum Intent representation generated using LLMs. The architecture includes the Service Intent Manager, Network-Compute Fabric, and Resource Infrastructure, each playing a critical role in transforming natural language business requests into actionable network tasks. We implemented this architecture and tested it by orchestrating video streaming services on a Kubernetes platform. The results demonstrate how IBN architecture supports the seamless translation of user intents into network operations, enabling autonomous network management and enhancing service provision across diverse domains.

Index Terms—Intent-based networking, Resource Orchestration, TM Forum Intents, LLMs, Autonomous Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing complexity of network management demands innovative solutions to automate and streamline network operations [1]–[3]. Intent-Based Networking (IBN), or Intent-driven Networking, has emerged as a promising approach to address this challenge. IBN leverages user-defined business network requirements, the Intents, to automate network management tasks. However, current IBN implementations often require users to possess expertise about unnecessary technical details to define these Intents, creating a significant barrier to adoption.

This paper presents a novel approach to IBN that leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) to simplify service deployment on cloud platforms, e.g., real-time video streaming applications, network services, etc. LLMs excel at understanding natural language, making them ideal for interpreting user requests expressed in plain English or other language. Our system helps users to define service deployment requests effortlessly using natural language. The LLM then processes these requests and translates them into a standardized TM

Forum (TMF) autonomous network framework. This standardized format ensures interoperability with multiple scenarios, allowing the different underlying components to understand and execute the user’s Intent readily. The LLM-based approach significantly simplifies defining service management and orchestration, facilitating the deployment of Intents, and improves the overall accessibility of IBN technology. Both industry and academia have previously explored the applicability of IBN in Network Management and Orchestration. However, our work fills a critical gap by adhering to industry standards for intent representation, ensuring seamless interoperability across diverse network environments.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses related works, and Section III details the proposed architecture. In Section V, we present the experimental results. Finally, in Section VI, we present the conclusions and outline potential future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Existing Frameworks

IBN has emerged as a promising approach for automating network management tasks within 5G and Beyond 5th Generation (B5G) networks [4]. Several researchers have explored the potential of IBN, highlighting its ability to simplify network operations. For instance, Njah et al. [5] proposed an IBN architecture that allows networks to adapt automatically to high-level user specifications (Intents) while hiding the underlying infrastructure complexity. This approach aligns with the findings of Jacobs et al. [6], who emphasize the benefit of IBN in reducing network management complexity by enabling operators to define high-level policies without needing low-level configurations. Similarly, Ribeiro et al. [7] explored the application of IBN for cloud and Software-Defined Networks (SDN), highlighting its role in automating network configuration and resource allocation based on operator intents, ultimately ensuring desired Quality of Service (QoS) levels.

Beyond automation, IBN offers additional advantages in managing advanced network deployments. Mehmood et al. [8] investigated the use of IBN for service orchestration in

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B5G networks using a simulation, leveraging the capabilities of modern service-based architectures. Similarly, Velasco et al. [7] explored using IBN to provide a high-level abstraction layer for network management, allowing operators to specify goals without burdening implementation details. However, implementing IBN introduces challenges related to the context-aware intent definition, stakeholder role management, standardization, and robust architectural considerations [9]. Barbosa et al. [1] proposed an architecture that enhances the Management and Orchestration of an End-to-End Network (E2E), integrating Voice-enabled Virtual Assistants with IBN and SDN solutions. Their architecture aims to improve industrial network management, orchestration efficiency, and flexibility while supporting B5G networks. It considers the adaptability to existing Network Orchestrators, Network Slice Managers, and SDNs.

To address the challenges concerning context-aware intent generation, LLMs emerge as a promising solution. LLMs excel at understanding context, inferring user intentions, and generating coherent responses, as demonstrated in various domains like conversational systems, code generation, and navigating complex knowledge graphs [10]–[12]. LLMs can understand user intent input and translate requests into clear and actionable network configurations. This fusion between IBN and LLMs has the potential to streamline configuration and management processes, leading to efficient and autonomous zero-touch network operations.

B. Standardization

Ensuring interoperability, reliability, and performance across diverse network environments necessitates the standardization of IBN. The TMF, a leading industry association, has actively spearheaded efforts in defining IBN standards. These initiatives aim to streamline user requests and service deployments through the power of LLMs. A core objective is to establish a common framework for IBN implementations, enabling seamless automation of network operations based on user intent [13].

Zeydan et al. [14] proposed intent standardization efforts, which focus on providing a structured framework for defining and implementing network intents. Similarly, Abbas et al. [15] highlight the significant progress in standardizing Service Assurance in Intent-Based Networking (SAIN) at the IETF and propose a closed-loop automation framework specifically for service assurance. In essence, the standardization of IBN, particularly when coupled with LLMs, is essential for advancing network automation and interoperability and enhancing the overall performance of communication networks. Our proposed architecture uses a clear separation between the user request and the actual deployment services and is compatible with the TMF intent representation and standards.

TMF is a global alliance of Telecommunications and technology companies. The alliance focuses on digital transformation while offering a foundational understanding of specialized topics, such as autonomous Networks, Generative AI, and Network Operations Support Systems. Moreover, it provides

courses and certifications to its members on diverse topics. The TMF enhances cooperation among Communication Service Providers (CSPs) through collaborative projects that address shared interests. These initiatives aim to develop procedures, blueprints, and domain-specific Open APIs to facilitate interoperability within complex service ecosystems.

One notable project is the Autonomous Network Project (ANP), which aims to define fully automated and innovative network and ICT services for vertical industry users and consumers. The ANP comprises three key components: the simplification of network architecture, the development of autonomous domains, and the implementation of automated intelligent operations.

Within the ANP, the Intent-driven Autonomous Networks project (IDAN) uses intent-based networking to automate network operations. The IDAN Project¹ has produced several open standards and interfaces that help CSPs to provide Network Services in a standardized way. Specifically, it has defined an Ontology for Intent [16], which details the structure and formalizes how to define the Intent, associated actions, the context of the Intent, dependencies, and the outcomes of the Intent. The IDAN project has also defined the Intent Management Profile [17], which transforms networks into utility-aware and self-adapting autonomous systems.

III. ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows the architecture designed to realize Intent-driven Management using TMF Standards for Autonomous Networks. This architecture has three main building blocks: the Service Intent Manager (SIM), the Network-Compute Fabric, and the Resource Infrastructure. It begins with the user, whose role is pivotal as they initiate the process by making a Natural Language Business Request. The request then goes to the SIM, which assesses the request and generates a corresponding TMF Intent representation in Turtle format [18]. The Network-Compute Fabric executes the validated intents by dynamically allocating network and computational resources. The Resource Infrastructure provides the underlying physical and virtual assets required for the network services, ensuring they are available and properly managed to support the autonomous operations.

A. The Service Intent Manager

The SIM plays an essential role in the architecture of intent-driven management with TMF Standards aimed at achieving Autonomous Networks. It is the intermediary between user requests and the underlying network infrastructure, ensuring that business intents are accurately interpreted, validated, and processed. The Intent Manager comprises four critical components: the Intent Generator, Intent Validator, Intent Extractor, and Domain Agent. Each element has a specific function to ensure the efficient handling of intents throughout its lifecycle.

The Intent Generator is the first component to engage with a user's natural language business request. Using the API

¹<https://www.tmfforum.org/catalysts/projects/C23.0.563>

Fig. 1. Proposed architecture.

facilities provided by LLMs, the intention behind the request is classified, and the appropriate TMF intent representation is selected. This classification is crucial as it decomposes the user's request into a structured intent that aligns with TMF standards. It is important to note that TMF categorizes intents into three hierarchical types: Business Intent, Service Intent, and Resource Intent. According to TMF specifications, a natural language request initially classified as a Business Intent needs translation into a Service Intent before being translated into a Resource Intent. The architecture simplifies this hierarchy by employing domain agents capable of handling different intents, thereby streamlining the entire process. The generated intent is then prepared for further processing, ensuring it captures the essential details of the user's original request.

Following the generation of an initial intent representation by the Intent Generator, the process transitions to the Intent Validation module for verification. This component validates the generated intent to ensure it meets the required format and standards. It checks for any errors or discrepancies in the representation, ensuring the intent is correctly structured and free of issues hindering further processing. Validation is critical as it guarantees that the intent adheres to the necessary guidelines before moving forward in the lifecycle.

Following validation, the Intent Extractor takes the validated intent and queries it, extracting the necessary information to process the request. The information moves to the downstream components, specifically the Network-Compute Fabric, which handles the actual execution of the request. The Intent Extractor ensures that all relevant data is accurately retrieved and ready for the subsequent stages of intent processing.

The Domain Agent is the final component within the SIM. It classifies the request's domain based on the extracted information, facilitating the network-computer fabric's efficient handling of the request. For instance, if the request pertains to maintenance, the Domain Agent classifies it as a service

intent, and it will be forwarded to the maintenance manager to perform automatic service maintenance.

Upon submission of the requests to the specific domain, the SIM generates an initial high-level report on the status, which serves as feedback to the user, completing the loop and providing insights into the request's progress. The SIM generally integrates these four components to streamline and transform user intents into actionable tasks within the network. SIM handles each task to maintain the integrity and efficiency of intent-driven management.

B. Network Compute Fabric and Resource Infrastructure

The Network Compute Fabric [19], a concept that considers the unification of both Communication and Computing. This new paradigm unifies the ecosystems, the application management, the execution environment, and the exposure of network & compute capabilities. The need for this block resides in the shift associated with the requirements. The Network Compute Fabric role is to be the entity responsible for managing and orchestrating services over the computing and communication resources. For this purpose, all the intents generated by the SMI are handled by this component. The Network Compute Fabric then decides how to fulfill the requests based on the existing resources. Interacting with the Resource Infrastructure requires the use of specialized controllers and translators who are responsible for requesting the services.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We tested the concept presented in Fig. 2 in a simulated environment to validate the proposed IBN architecture. The environment setup included GPT-3.5 Turbo to process NLP requests, generate TM Forum service intents, and a K3s Kubernetes Cluster² to deploy and manage services. We used TM Forum Ontology as a database to fine-tune GPT-3.5. A Kubernetes Specialized Controller and custom-developed

²<https://k3s.io/>

Fig. 2. Experimental setup.

script were utilized to extract information about the services deployed within the Kubernetes cluster. The entire pipeline was implemented using Python, and the system was tested in an ASUS TUF Gaming F16 FX607JV Laptop running Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS. Key performance metrics measured included:

- Relevance of the extracted intent.
- Latency to generate a TM Forum Intent.
- Service deployment time (to evaluate the latency of a new service deployment into the Kubernetes cluster).
- Resource utilization to assess the efficiency of resource allocation and utilization.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we present the proposed method's results, focusing on three key aspects: intent representation, deployment file generation, and analysis of the method's latency.

The initial step involves the transformation of the natural language business requests into a structured format using TM Forum standards. Fig. 1 shows the user request and the corresponding intent representation. The user requests are decomposed into Turtle representations according to TM Forum standards, making them ready for querying and searching by the corresponding network devices and programs. This representation is stored in a file for further Intent processing when implementing the Validation and Reporting functions.

Following intent representation, Network Compute-Fabric will generate the deployment files by translating user intents into network configuration instructions through tailored translators communicating with the Resource Infrastructure controllers. These deployment files contain the essential commands to configure network devices and resources. In our implementation, the deployment file is a Kubernetes (K8s) manifest file in YAML format, designed for deploying video streaming services on a Kubernetes platform. We first extract the necessary information from the intent representation and the existing network configuration to create this deployment file. The resulting Kubernetes manifest file (Fig. 4) serves as a

```

User Request: I want to stream live video from my camera and to detect the objects
inside the live video using YOLOv8 algorithm. Please deploy the object detection in a
k8s platform using low latency and give GPU support if available. The stream should
be uninterrupted.

Corresponding TMF Intent

@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix lcn: <http://tlo.models.tnforum.org/tlo/v1.0.0/IntentCommonModel#> .
@prefix lno: <http://tlo.models.tnforum.org/tlo/v1.0.0/IntentManagementOntology#> .
@prefix pbl: <http://tlo.models.tnforum.org/tlo/v1.0.0/ProposalBestIntent#> .
@prefix cat: <http://www.operator.com/Catalog#> .
@prefix tech: <http://www.sdo.org/Technology#> .
@prefix met: <http://www.sdo.org/TelecomMetrics/Version_1.0#> .
@prefix ti: <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#> .
@prefix ex: <http://www.example.org/IntentNamespace#> .
@prefix iv: <https://tnforum.org/2021/07/IntentValidity#> .
@prefix itv: <https://tnforum.org/2021/07/IntentTemporalValidity#> .
@prefix cem: <http://tlo.labs.tnforum.org/tlo/v1.0.0/CatalystExtensionModel#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix arc: <http://tlo.models.tnforum.org/tlo/v1.0.0/IntentAcceptanceControl/> .

#### Intent #####
#
# This intent represents the deployment and business request for live video streaming
# and object detection using YOLOv8 on a Kubernetes platform.

ex:VideoStreaming_ObjectDetection_Intent
  a lcn:Intent ;
  rdfs:comment "Intent for deploying and operating live video object detection service" ;
  lno:IntentOwner ex:Admin ;
  cem:layer "business, deployment" ;
  arc:IntentRejectionReasonOverride lno:SuccessfulHandlingNotExpected ;
  arc:updateRejectionReasonOverride lno:SuccessfulHandlingNotExpected ;
  lcn:hasExpectation ex:Deployment_Expectation ;
  ex:Property_Expectation ;

#### Deployment Expectation #####
#
ex:Deployment_Expectation
  a lcn:DeploymentExpectation ;
  lcn:target ex:T1_Deployment_Target ;
  lcn:allof [ rdfs:member ex:P1_Deployment_Node ;
            rdfs:member ex:P2_GPU_Support ;
            ] ;

ex:T1_Deployment_Target
  a lcn:IndividualTarget ;
  lcn:OneElementOf [ lcn:elementType tech:K8sDeployment ] ;

ex:P1_Deployment_Node
  a lcn:Parameter ;
  lcn:deploymentDescription "Deploy on Node_1 within k8s platform" ;
  lcn:deploymentType tech:low ;

ex:P2_GPU_Support
  a lcn:Parameter ;
  lcn:deploymentResource tech:GPUSupport ;
  lcn:ifAvailable "true" ;

```

Fig. 3. User request and corresponding Intent using TMF standard.

```

apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  labels:
    app: test-app
    name: test-deployment
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: test-app
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: test-app
    spec:
      affinity:
        nodeAffinity:
          requiredDuringSchedulingIgnoredDuringExecution:
            nodeSelectorTerms:
              - matchExpressions:
                  - key: latency
                    operator: In
                    values:
                      - low
      containers:
        - image: nginx:latest
          name: test-container
          resources:
            limits:
              cpu: 500m
              memory: 256Mi
            requests:
              cpu: 250m
              memory: 128Mi

```

Fig. 4. Sample K8S manifest file.

Fig. 5. Execution time distribution.

blueprint for deploying and migrating video streaming services across various nodes within the Kubernetes cluster.

Following the Proof of Concept implementation of the Architecture, we collected some results regarding the latency of the process we are proposing. Fig. 5 shows the time from receiving a request to its deployment and subsequent reporting. Since our current deployment is centered on a single use case (video streaming), the validation process occurs in real-time as part of the overall request processing. Therefore, we measured the time required for intent generation, manifest file generation, and service migration. The average time needed for intent generation is 11, 08; $\sigma = 4.4$ seconds, while generating the Kubernetes manifest file takes 0.263; $\sigma = 0.19$ seconds. The actual deployment process takes around 20 seconds.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an architecture for Intent-Based Networking (IBN) that leverages TM Forum standards and Large

Language Models (LLMs) to facilitate autonomous network management. This approach enables users to express service requests in natural language, streamlining network operations and translating user intent into actionable network tasks. To validate this approach, we implemented the proposed architecture and tested its performance on a Kubernetes platform for video streaming services. These tests demonstrated the architecture's capability to balance user requests with efficient network and resource management effectively. The results indicate that our IBN framework facilitates seamless intent translation, enabling more autonomous network management across diverse domains.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Barbosa, J. P. Fonseca, M. Araújo, and D. Corujo, "Vinia: Voice-enabled intent-based networking for industrial automation," *Comput. Sci. Inf. Syst.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 395–418, 2024.
- [2] J. McNamara and et al., "Nlp powered intent based network management for private 5g networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 36642–36657, 2023.
- [3] K. Mehmood, K. Kravlevska, and D. Palma, "Intent-driven autonomous network and service management in future cellular networks: A structured literature review," *Computer Networks*, vol. 220, p. 109477, 2023.
- [4] I. Ahmad and et al., "Security in intent-based networking: Challenges and solutions," in *2023 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN)*, pp. 296–301, IEEE, 2023.
- [5] Y. Njah, A. Leivadreas, J. Violos, and M. Falkner, "Toward intent-based network automation for smart environments: A healthcare 4.0 use case," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 136565–136576, 2023.
- [6] A. S. Jacobs and et al., "Refining network intents for self-driving networks," in *Proceedings of the Afternoon Workshop on Self-Driving Networks*, pp. 15–21, 2018.
- [7] R. H. Ribeiro and et al., "A bottom-up approach for extracting network intents," in *Advanced Information Networking and Applications: Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications (AINA-2020)*, pp. 858–870, Springer, 2020.
- [8] K. Mehmood, D. Palma, and K. Kravlevska, "Mission-critical public safety networking: An intent-driven service orchestration perspective," in *2022 IEEE 8th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, pp. 37–42, IEEE, 2022.
- [9] K. Mehmood, K. Kravlevska, and D. Palma, "Intent-driven autonomous network and service management in future cellular networks: A structured literature review," *Computer Networks*, vol. 220, p. 109477, 2023.
- [10] Y. Deng and et al., "Prompting and evaluating large language models for proactive dialogues: Clarification, target-guided, and non-collaboration," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.13626*, 2023.
- [11] K. Patil and B. Desai, "Leveraging llm for zero-day exploit detection in cloud networks," *Asian American Research Letters Journal*, vol. 1, no. 4, 2024.
- [12] E. Nijkamp and et al., "Codegen: An open large language model for code with multi-turn program synthesis," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.13474*, 2022.
- [13] D. Borsatti, W. Cerroni, and S. Clayman, "From category theory to functional programming: A formal representation of intent," in *2022 IEEE 8th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, pp. 31–36, IEEE, 2022.
- [14] E. Zeydan and Y. Turk, "Recent advances in intent-based networking: A survey," in *2020 IEEE 91st Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2020-Spring)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 2020.
- [15] K. Abbas, T. A. Khan, M. Afaq, and W.-C. Song, "Network slice lifecycle management for 5g mobile networks: An intent-based networking approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 80128–80146, 2021.
- [16] T. Forum, "Tr290 intent common model," tech report, 2023.
- [17] T. Forum, "Tmf921a intent management api profile," tech report, 2022.
- [18] M. Xie and et al., "Intent-driven management for multi-vertical end-to-end network slicing services," in *2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, pp. 1285–1291, IEEE, 2022.
- [19] A. Sefidcon, W. John, M. Opsenica, and B. Skubic, "The network compute fabric – advancing digital transformation with ever-present service continuity," *Ericsson Technology Review*, vol. 2021, pp. 2–11, June 2021.